

SPATIAL AND TEMPORAL ANALYSIS ON SPRAT (*Sprattus sprattus* L.) SURVEYS CATCH PER UNIT EFFORT AND CATCH PER UNIT AREA FROM BULGARIAN MARINE ZONE

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Abstract. Sprat (*Sprattus sprattus* L.) is a keynote species in the Black Sea, and stock dynamics is highly affected by the fisheries and environmental conditions. Another important feature of the species is cyclic nature of its spawning stock biomass and recruitment. Thus, seasonal fishery independent surveys are crucial for stock condition evaluation and managerial decisions for sustainable exploitation. Sprat surveys under DCF (DCR199/2000 EC) were conducted in spring 2007–2010 and autumn 2015–2018. The present paper considers the use of GIS application which is frequently used as a supplementary tool for spatial analyses of fisheries activities including commercial fishing, impacts of IUU fishing, by-catch, unintentional catch of protected species, etc. Analyses are to support the follow-up assessment and decision-making process. Principal component analysis (PCA) is applied to explain biomass variability within the stratified survey area as well as population distribution analysis, based on the survey results. High variability was identified in both parameters Catch per unit area (CPUA) and Catch per unit effort (CPUE) within different seasons and years. PCA and stock distribution analysis results are explained in the view of stock biomass distribution within the stratified survey area.

Keywords: GIS application, stock assessment, PCA, CPUA, stock distribution.

AIMS AND BACKGROUND

The present paper introduces multi-objective approach^{1,2} in stock survey data analyses to ensure better understanding of results and distribution of the studied

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species and to support further the decision-making process. The stock assessment results are crucial for proper management of fish stocks and it usually introduces a wide array of biological data thus it is of significance importance that the surveys are conducted within the actual area of the stock geographical distribution. In the above discussed matter GIS (Ref. 3) is undoubtedly adequate in order to help the visualisation of data followed by the respective spatial analyses.

A central challenge in fisheries ecology is to understand why species abundance changes over time^{4,5}. Consequently, the majority of fisheries research focuses on temporal variability of fish populations⁶. Within this context, demographic (i.e. population abundance) and environmental variables are averaged over large geographic areas, and their degree of correlation is then examined^{7,8}. Relevant studies^{9–11} in the Black Sea describes the distribution and state of the sprat and small pelagic stocks in the recent years.

EXPERIMENTAL

The generalised flow-chart of GIS procedures carried out is presented in Fig. 1 and ‘raw’ data loaded to feed the algorithm execution is based on the trawl surveys which have been carried out deliverables.

Fig. 1. GIS procedures flowchart

Based on the above described procedures are delivered the maps of the trawl expeditions (Figs 2 and 3). The excel tables with post-expedition data on CPOA and biomass were integrated into GIS by using the trawling locations coordinate records. The cited locations were subsequently exported as georeferenced points in ESRI shapefile format, thus containing the values on CPOA and biomass in the shapefile attribute tables. Later on, the cited values were interpolated into grids using inverse distance weighting (IDW), with the interpolation procedures applied for each of the five species separately, and each expedition separately. Finally,

the resulting raster files were reclassified converting the quantitative data from stretched values into interval breaks. The interpolation results were illustrated as a set of digital maps. The analysis results prove that GIS represents an effective supplementary tool in fisheries assessments, especially when using IDW.

Fig. 2. Trawling sites map – first expedition

Fig. 4. GIS visualisation of CPUA – first expedition

Fig. 5. GIS visualisation of stock biomass – first expedition

Fig. 6. GIS visualisation of CPUA – second expedition

Fig. 7. GIS visualisation of stock biomass – second expedition

Based on the survey results the stock distribution has been studied by depths (Figs 8–16).

Fig. 8. Stock distribution by depths – stratified stock trawl survey – spring 2007

Fig. 9. Stock distribution by depths – stratified stock trawl survey – spring 2008

Fig. 10. Stock distribution by depths – stratified stock trawl survey – spring 2009

Fig. 11. Stock distribution by depths – stratified stock trawl survey – spring 2010

Fig. 12. Stock distribution by depths – stratified stock trawl survey – autumn 2015

Fig. 13. Stock distribution by depths – stratified stock trawl survey – summer 2016

Fig. 14. Stock distribution by depths – stratified stock trawl survey – autumn 2016

Fig. 15. Stock distribution by depths – stratified stock trawl survey – spring 2017

Fig. 16. Stock distribution by depths – stratified stock trawl survey – autumn 2017

PCA analysis is used to explain the stock distribution variations (Fig. 17).

Fig. 17. PCA (stock distribution explanation by depths)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Reclassified raster files visualising CPUA and spatial distribution of biomass were produced (Figs 4–7) as a result of the interpolations carried out in Arc GIS environment.

Stock distribution analysis outcome shows that the maximum CPUA values observed are registered at depths: 74 m (16 417 kg/km²) – 2007 spring survey, 49.5 m (25 699.87 kg/km²) – 2008 spring survey, 49.1 m (27 500 kg/km²) – 2009 spring survey, 30.5 m (38 091.50 kg/km²) – 2010 spring survey; 55.6 m (28 926.26 kg/km²) – 2015 autumn survey, 78.4 (5237.1738 kg/km²) – 2016 summer survey, 63.2 m (11 171.51 kg/km²) – 2016 autumn survey, 80.1 m (3491.10 kg/km²) – 2017 spring survey and 53 m (3615.78 kg/km²) – 2017 autumn survey. Stock distribution analysis by depths shows that highest stock abundance indices are observed in: stratum 2 (50–70 m) in 2007, stratum 1 (10–30 m) in 2008, stratum 1 in 2009, stratum 2 in 2010, stratum 2 in 2015, stratum 3 (75–100 m) in the summer and stratum 2 in the autumn 2016, stratum 3 in the spring survey and stratum 1 in the autumn 2017. In addition to stock distribution by depths analysis the present study aims to present an explanation of stock variance within the strata and applied further is PCA analysis (Fig. 17). The results delivered shows that PC1 (cumulative CPUA in Stratum 1 by years) and PC2 (cumulative CPUA in Stratum 2 by years) explain the stock variance with highest values (96.7549 and 26.4004%, respectively) hence survey depths ranging from 10 to 75 m are the most informative in identifying the stock abundance indices.

Stock distribution variance by depths may be further linked to temperature, food availability or other environmental factors variations as well as specifics in seasonality, timing and physiology of species under analysis.

CONCLUSIONS

GIS and geospatial data on target fish species are extremely useful in fisheries analyses and stock assessments thanks to their highly spatial-dimensional properties. Data are easy to store, process, analyse and visualise. Therefore, the GIS-aided surveys are expected to become one of the main supplementary tools in help of the scientifically based fisheries decision-making focused on the Bulgarian Black Sea.

High variability was identified in both parameters C_{PUA} and C_{PUE} within different seasons and years; stock distribution charts appear effective tool in analysis of distribution analysis and may be further linked with environmental data for variances explanation.

PCA and other statistical tools are effective supplementary tools, which can be successfully implemented in stock assessment data analysis and respectively they can also contribute to quality of the decision-making process and better understanding of stock dynamics.

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